

THE INFLUENCE OF LEARNING STRATEGIES AND DIGITAL LITERACY OF CIVIC EDUCATION LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL - LIMA PULUH KOTA REGENCY, INDONESIA

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Abstract

This research was about the influence of learning strategies and digital literacy on learning outcomes in the civic education field of study at Senior High School (SHS) - Lima Puluh Kota Regency. This research aims to describe the factors that influence Civics learning outcomes, including: 1) the influence of learning strategies on Civics learning outcomes; and 2) the influence of digital literacy on civics learning outcomes. This type of research is quantitative research using quantitative data collection and analysis methods to answer the research problem formulation. The research population was all high school students who took part in citizenship lessons in the Limapuluh Kota district. Sampling in this research used the Multistage Sampling technique. Surveys and questionnaires were data collection techniques used in this research. To determine the validity of the instrument, Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis was used to calculate reliability using Cronbach's Alpha formula. The data analysis technique used in this research is the path analysis approach using the AMOS method, which previously required normality and linearity tests. Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that there was a significant influence between the research variables. There is the influence of learning strategies on civics learning outcomes and the influence of digital literacy on civics learning outcomes.

Keywords: Influence, Learning Strategies, Digital Literacy, Learning Outcomes, Civic Education.

INTRODUCTION

Civic education subjects are included in the "Pancasila" subject application as the government's commitment to implementing of Government Regulation No. 4/2022 concerning "National Education Standards". Starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, the Pancasila education theme in the Merdeka curriculum will be implemented in more than 140,000 early childhood education, elementary, junior, and higher education units throughout Indonesia as required by "Pancasila" and 1945 (Harefa & Lase, 2023). Civic education is an important thing instilled especially through formal and informal knowledge transfer processes. The position of civics Education subjects has become an obligation to be included in the education curriculum so that it is in line with those stated in the national education goals in Government Regulation Number No. 4/2022 (Helda & Syahrani, 2022).

Student learning outcomes are one of the problems in the world of education. Learning activities must be followed by students to achieve good learning outcomes. Learning outcomes are abilities that participants gain from learning experiences. Changes in behavior that are positive and relatively permanent in people who learn are the result of learning activities. If someone can identify changes in themselves, it can be said that they have learned something. Changes in thinking capacity, abilities, or attitudes regarding objects are among them (Siregar, 2019). Teaching and learning methods in the era of the fourth industrial revolution have changed in line with technological advances. The internet and computers are technologies that make the learning process easier.

The Indonesian government began promoting three types of literacy in 2017, one of which is digital literacy. Digital literacy is the ability to use digital media, communication tools, or networks to obtain, assess, produce, and use information in a healthy, wise, intelligent, precise, thorough, and law-abiding way to establish connections and communicate with other people (Nasrullah et al., 2017). In line with this, Wibawa (2018) stated that students must also know how to use technology and information, as well as the ability to find, organize, and communicate information.

The importance of digital literacy is reflected in almost all aspects of modern life. In education, digital literacy is needed to support effective learning and develop skills that are relevant to the times. In the workplace, the ability to adapt to technology and use digital tools is key to increasing productivity and competitiveness. In addition, in everyday life, digital literacy allows individuals to engage in digital culture, communicate, search for information, and access services online (Martin, 2006). Digital literacy refers to an individual's skills, knowledge, and understanding of digital technology. This includes the ability to use hardware (such as computers, and smartphones) and software (apps, digital platforms) effectively. Apart from that, digital literacy also includes the ability to evaluate, create, and collaborate in a digital environment (Eshet & Alkalai, 2004).

Digital literacy in schools is a student's ability to utilize digital media, such as communication tools, internet networks, and so on wisely, intelligently, carefully, and appropriately according to their use. Digital literacy includes the ability to discover, do, evaluate, use, create, and utilize it wisely. Implementing digital literacy in schools can make students wiser in using technology and help increase digital literacy among underrepresented groups. Examples of implementing digital literacy in schools include communicating with teachers or friends using social media, sending school assignments via e-mail, and learning online (Hockly, 2012).

Although the importance of digital literacy is recognized, there are several challenges faced in developing this skill. According to A'yuni (2015), the main challenges include access gaps, where some individuals or communities do not have adequate access to technology or internet connections. Additionally, there are also challenges in educational curricula that may not emphasize enough on developing relevant digital skills. Increasing digital literacy has a significant impact on society. In the education sector, this can increase access to online educational resources and support distance learning. In the economic field, digital literacy enables greater job opportunities and business innovation. In a social context, increasing digital literacy can also expand social networks, enable global collaboration, and promote cultural exchange (Asari, 2010).

Apart from digital literacy, learning strategies also greatly determine students' learning success. The use of less varied learning strategies can make students less active, making them boring, and resulting in students not absorbing the material presented by the teacher. In this case, teachers must use active learning strategies such as exchanging knowledge and finding information themselves to gain knowledge in learning so that they can achieve learning goals (Erianjoni et al., 2023). A teacher must master various learning strategies to create effective learning so that students can play an active role in the learning process and achieve maximum learning outcomes.

Learning strategies are the methods chosen and used by teachers to convey learning materials so that it makes it easier for students to receive, understand, process, store, and produce learning materials (Djamarah, 2010).

Hidayat (2019) explains that learning strategies are the methods chosen to convey learning material in a certain environment. By using a variety of learning strategies, students are indirectly trained to be more confident during the learning process, grow courage in positive matters, increase student learning motivation, increase student creativity, listen carefully, and summarize ideas so that students can be more productive in learning.

Based on the results of observations made by the author, it appears that the civic education subject is still low in student interest because this learning is always associated with long and extensive reading. This is reflected in each student's actions, starting from the attitudes, responsibilities, and learning achievement values of the students themselves.

Likewise, when it comes to carrying out assignments, they are often neglectful and negligent, such as when collecting assignments or carrying out questions or other assignments, not ignoring the material in a class by the teacher, some students feel they experience problems when working on tests or exams. semester because it is considered too difficult in some subjects/material which results in students' grades not being optimal.

Apart from that, students also experience difficulties in understanding and are less thorough when it comes to material regarding the Constitution as well as Indonesian history and state regulations. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that students' academic achievements are considered low. Several students of class XI Natural Science 4 of Senior High School (SHS) 1 Lareh Sago Halaban said the same thing as SHS students who assumed that civics subjects were difficult to memorize and understand their meaning. According to students, it took a long time to translate the meaning and work on the questions, because they had to be careful to understand them over and over again, and if there were errors in the notes, the recording had to be played back from the beginning.

Based on an initial survey of student learning outcomes at class XI Natural Science 4 of SHS with a total of 33 students, the reality found in the field reached an average of 68.9 for cognitive scores, lower than the Minimum Completion Criteria (MCC) set at 78; with only 39.39% (low) students achieving completeness.

This shows that so far teachers as educators have not paid attention to school culture, learning activities, and motivation. Apart from that, they do not implement learning strategies that can activate students, attract attention, facilitate student participation in learning, and make the transfer of knowledge more enjoyable, so that learning can increase learning outcomes. The objective that is the basis of this research is to empirically explore the influence of learning strategies and digital literacy on civics learning outcomes.

METHOD

The study of the problem that the researcher formulated based on the research objectives, the basis for the researcher to choose a method that is believed to be appropriate for this research and reliable, is a quantitative research method approach.

The sample size uses the Slovin formula with a population of 3,390. Slovin's formula is as follows (Yudiawan et al., 2021).

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size

e = margin of error (then the sample size is 358 students)

Surveys and questionnaires are data collection techniques used in this quantitative research. Both techniques involve collecting data from respondents through questionnaires or interviews. Surveys are data collection techniques carried out by sending questionnaires to respondents, either by letter, email, or social media. Respondents were asked to fill out the questionnaire and return it to the researcher. Surveys are often used to collect data about respondents' opinions, attitudes, or behavior (Candra et al., 2023). This research study is based on five data as variables that have been determined by researchers, namely student learning outcome variables (Y), learning strategies (X1), school culture (X2), learning activities (X3), digital literacy (X4) and learning motivation (X5), based on data analysis, it is known that the average price, standard savings, mode and median, frequency distribution and histogram graph are as follows.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis Results

3.1.1 Description of Student Learning Outcome Variable Data

Empirically, the data description of student learning outcome variables has a score range of 52.42, namely with the lowest score of 45 and the highest score of 97.42. Based on the results of data analysis, researchers found an average score of 85.41, with a standard deviation of 10.19, median of 89.25, mode 60, number of classes 6, and class length of 10. For more details, see Table 1 below.

Table 1: Description of Learning Outcome Data

N	Valid	385
	Missing	0
Mean		85.4057
Std. Error of Mean		0.51946
Median		89.2500
Mode		60.00
Std. Deviation		10.19249
Variance		103.887
Minimum		45.00
Maximum		97.42
Sum		32881.21

Based on the trend distribution as depicted in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Distribution of Learning Outcome Data

Learning Outcomes					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	41-50	6	1.6	1.6	1.6
	51-60	22	5.7	5.7	7.3
	61-70	12	3.1	3.1	10.4
	71-80	32	8.3	8.3	18.7
	81-90	153	39.7	39.7	58.4
	91-100	160	41.6	41.6	100.0
Total		385	100.0	100.0	

Furthermore, the trend in the distribution of student learning outcomes (Y) above is depicted in a bar diagram as depicted in the Fig 2 below.

Figure 1: Graph of Student Learning Results

3.1.2 Description of Digital Literacy Variables

The Digital Literacy variable (X4), empirically found a score range of 119, with the lowest score being 110 and the highest score being 229. Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that the average score was 178.73, with a standard deviation of 21.095, median of 180, mode 172, and number of classes. 6. and class length 20. For more details, see Table 3 below.

Table 3: Description of Digital Literacy data

N	Valid	385
	Missing	0
Mean		178.73
Std. Error of Mean		1.075
Median		180.00
Mode		172
Std. Deviation		21.095
Variance		444.980
Minimum		110
Maximum		229
Sum		68810

Based on the results of these calculations, it was found that the criteria for digital literacy level with distribution tendencies were as depicted in the Table 4 below.

Table 4: Distribution of Digital Literacy Tendencies

Digital Literasi		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	101-130	6	1.6	1.6	1.6
	131-150	36	9.4	9.4	10.9
	151-170	70	18.2	18.2	29.1
	171-190	173	44.9	44.9	74.0
	191-210	77	20.0	20.0	94.0
	211-230	23	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total		385	100.0	100.0	

Below is the trend in the distribution of Digital Literacy (X4) levels, as depicted in Fig 2 below.

Figure 2. Digital Literacy Graph

Furthermore, in the analysis of the influence of digital literacy (X4) on student learning outcomes (Y), the value $t = -3.574$ at sign = 0.000 is obtained, thus the hypothesis is accepted $\alpha = 0.0$, so it can be categorized in this research study as very significant. Based on the significance level of 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a direct influence of digital literacy (X4) on student learning outcomes (Y).

3.2 Discussion

3.2.1 The Influence of Learning Strategies on Civics Learning Outcomes

Learning strategies are needed to achieve the maximum possible results. Efficient learning can be achieved if you can use appropriate learning strategies (Simsek & Balaban, 2010). Geijsel & Meijers (2005) said that the learning process at school is the core of school activities. Learning must be planned and organized so that it runs effectively and efficiently. Students do not easily accept the lesson material as a whole. Therefore, teachers must have strategies for handling and distributing material in a class. Geijsel & Meijers (2005) said that the learning strategies used by teachers had more or less an impact on the learning process. This impact is expected to provide better results in the learning process. The chosen learning strategy should be considered carefully because the learning strategy must be flexible according to the

needs of the class and the material being presented by the teacher. Mastering various learning strategies is one of the teacher's efforts to overcome problems during the learning process. Especially the problem of low student learning outcomes.

The learning strategies implemented have a significant influence on civics learning outcomes. Research shows that implementing learning strategies that focus on interactivity and collective empowerment of students in the learning process can positively influence their learning outcomes. A cooperative approach without individual assessment may foster cooperation among students, improve understanding of the material, and result in better achievement.

A teacher carries out teaching in various forms. One way to achieve learning that students like is by applying learning strategies. The learning strategy used must be adapted to the learning material and student character. For this reason, teachers need to carry out varied learning strategies by doing:

First, a teacher must choose a learning strategy that suits the material. The learning material that will be explained must be adapted to the learning strategy. In the learning process, students will feel effective if the strategies used are also to the student's character. The more varied the strategies used, the more effective learning will be. Students will study actively so that it can influence their learning outcomes later.

Second, a teacher should use technology in the learning process. In modern times like this, technology is certainly familiar to all of us. Many people already use technology, both at simple and complex levels. This also needs to be applied in the classroom as a teaching strategy by teachers. By utilizing technology, learning becomes more effective and will certainly be closer to students whose daily lives also interact with technology. Currently, many media can be used to make the learning atmosphere more interactive. Teachers can use interactive whiteboards, computers, and even smartphones that can display images and videos to support the learning process. Using auxiliary media like this will make it easier for students to understand material that is difficult to understand if it is only limited to theory or text.

Third, a teacher must also carry out outdoor learning activities. Studying in class sometimes makes students bored. The reason is that some students feel they cannot see the application of the material studied directly. Therefore, teachers can apply outdoor learning strategies to refresh students' brains. You don't have to go far away, teachers can invite students to the environment around the school to link the learning theories that have been taught with facts that occur in the field. When you want to do outdoor learning, it's a good idea to be well-prepared. Starting from security to time. Don't let learning activities outside the classroom become just a play agenda for children.

Fourth, a teacher should provide assessment and appreciation to students. Assessment is one of the important things after learning activities are carried out. Assessment is used to measure the extent to which students have mastered the material that has been given. Assessment also serves as a means of reflection for teachers in teaching. Whether the methods, media, and strategies applied so far are suitable for the students or not. Not only giving assessments but also trying to always give appreciation to students or their learning efforts so far. Students who are given appreciation from their teachers feel more appreciated and will be more enthusiastic about learning in the future.

3.2.2 The Influence of Digital Literacy on Civics Learning Outcomes

The importance of digital literacy is reflected in almost all aspects of modern life. In education, digital literacy is needed to support effective learning and develop skills that are relevant to the times. In the workplace, the ability to adapt to technology and use digital tools is key to increasing productivity and competitiveness. In addition, in everyday life, digital literacy allows individuals to engage in digital culture, communicate, search for information, and access services online (Martin & Grudziecky, 2006).

Strong digital literacy provides major benefits in civics learning outcomes. Students with good digital literacy skills can be more effective in accessing information, analyzing digital content, and using technology in the learning process. The existence of strong digital literacy can support the understanding of the material and provide wider access to learning resources. Nurramdani et al (2023) stated that students' literacy skills influence their lives.

The higher a student's digital literacy skills, the broader their insight will be. On the other hand, students whose digital literacy skills are low in quality will also have little or narrow insight. This will have an impact on student learning motivation. Concrete evidence of success in learning is learning outcomes. Learning outcomes will determine the next steps that the teacher must take regarding learning evaluation activities. Cognitive, affective, and psychomotor are aspects of learning outcomes.

From the research results, it can be seen that digital literacy has a big influence on student learning outcomes. Students who use digital literacy well and according to their needs in the learning process will have an impact on improving learning outcomes. Students will be more creative in using digital literacy.

Digital literacy is a skill needed for living, learning, and carrying out activities in society along with the development of access to information and communication. The use of digital media among students is sometimes not appropriate. Sometimes the information they receive from the media is not necessarily the truth, they only see it from one side so hoax news emerges. The efforts that teachers can make in the learning process are as follows:

First, learn from trusted sources. Obtaining information from trusted sources is the first step in increasing digital literacy. Be sure to check if the source has legitimate accreditation and if they have a good reputation for providing accurate information.

Second, motivation improves information-seeking skills. Improving the ability to search for information online is also an important factor in increasing digital literacy. By learning how to search for information effectively and efficiently, we can obtain accurate information more easily and quickly.

Third, improve analytical skills. Improving analytical skills is also an important factor in increasing digital literacy. Students must learn to recognize and examine various aspects of the information they receive, such as the source, truth, and purpose behind the information.

Fourth, get involved in online communities. Getting involved in online communities can help improve digital literacy. We can participate in online discussions, forums, and groups to share knowledge and experiences with others who share the same interests. It can also help us gain more information and increase our social network.

CONCLUSION

The research results show that factors such as innovative learning strategies and strong digital literacy have a significant influence on student learning outcomes in the field of civics studies at SHS Lima Puluh Kota Regency. Solid integration between these elements can create a learning environment that promotes better academic achievement for students. Strong digital literacy significantly influences student learning outcomes.

Students' skill levels in managing digital information, analyzing online data, and using technology impact their ability to access, understand, and apply the knowledge they gain. Innovative and technology-based learning strategies provide a big boost to civics learning outcomes at SHS Lima Puluh Kota Regency.

The use of interactive methods and technology in learning provides better opportunities for students to be actively and deeply involved in the learning process, increasing their understanding of the subject matter. Strong digital literacy significantly influences student learning outcomes. Students' skill levels in managing digital information, analyzing online data, and using technology impact their ability to access, understand, and apply the knowledge they gain.

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